

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The importance of interactive methods that develop listening skills in foreign language teaching. This article discusses the importance of interactive methods used to teach listening skills and some terms related to teaching listening skills.

Keywords: audio segment, video segment, interview, acoustic apperception, special exercises, auditory exercises, active listening

Listening or listening comprehension is one of the most important components of foreign language learning. Listening in language learning is the ability to correctly receive and interpret messages in the communication process. Listening is the key to all effective communication.

Listening is paying attention to sounds and trying to make sense of them. However, some have previously assumed that it is a passive activity, where the listener must distinguish between sounds, understand words and speech structures, interpret intonations, and retain the information gathered for interpretation in context. is an active process. There are two distinct processes or methods involved in listening; top-down and bottom-up process. Benet points out that listening is a one-way or two-way process. Both processes occur spontaneously and are thus interrelated.

Studies show that an average of 45% is spent listening, compared to 30% speaking, 16% reading, and 9% writing [1, 82]. That is, by any standard, a lot of time spent listening. That's why it's worth spending a little more time to ensure you're listening effectively.

According to sources, listening is not the same as hearing. Hearing refers to the sounds that enter your ears. This is done automatically by your physical hearing, unless you have hearing problems. But listening requires more than that: it requires mental and sometimes physical attention and concentration. Listening is not just about the story, but about how it is told, the use of language and voice, and how the other person uses their body. should pay attention. In other words, it means being aware of verbal and non-verbal messages. Your ability to listen effectively depends on your ability to receive and understand these messages. That's why sharpening is not a passive process.

Draws a contrast between audience materials and the interests of audience researchers and classroom practitioners to develop metacognitive knowledge by increasing listeners' and listeners' awareness of listening processes. Teaching students how to listen is very important. This shifts the focus of listening practice from product to process and shifts the responsibility for learning from the teacher to the student, thereby helping students become self-directed learners [3, 103].

It is worth noting that the listener should participate in this process at least as much as the speaker, listen to the conversation and perceive it. The term "active listening" is used to describe this process of full participation.

Listening comprehension is a three-stage activity, the content of the speech is perceived, learned and understood behind the general auditory perception (acoustic apperception), distinguishing the sound side of words (phonemic) and understanding the essence.

Effective, up-to-date methods of teaching listening skills are available, along with interactive exercises and multimedia resources. Listening skills are effectively taught through simple, fun activities that focus more on the learning process than on the end product.

One of the effective ways to strengthen listening skills in language teaching is to organize mutual interviews. Learners can organize a specific listening process by being assigned to small groups of two or three. It provides an opportunity to develop listening skills through interaction. Larger group activities are also a useful way to teach listeners listening skills.

Listeners don't care about everything; they listen selectively according to the purpose of the task. This in turn determines the type of listening required and how listeners approach the task.

The system of listening comprehension (auditory) exercises is divided into two types according to their purpose: special and non-special exercises. In non-specific exercises, listening comprehension is taught orally. Therefore, organizing a lesson in a foreign language is one of the stages of teaching listening comprehension. Special exercises are divided into preparation for listening comprehension and pure speaking exercises. Listening skills can also be developed through audio segments, online podcasts, educational lectures, and other audio messages. In order for this process to be organized effectively, the necessary environment and conditions must be created. In addition, it is necessary to repeat the exercises.

Another useful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments, including short sketches, news programs, documentaries, interview segments, and dramatic and comedic material. As with the audio segments, the part and length of the video segment is chosen based on the skill level of the students.

By analyzing task requirements during listening, activating the necessary listening processes, making relevant predictions, monitoring their understanding, and evaluating the success of their approach, they are using metacognitive knowledge to understand successful listening. This is essential for the development of self-directed learning.

The process of listening comprehension includes mechanisms such as speech perception, auditory memory, speaking inside, comparison, anticipation (precomprehension), logical understanding. As a result of the formation of these mechanisms, students' listening comprehension skills are formed in the process of language learning. Listening comprehension skills are formed and developed due to necessary exercises in a foreign language. The following three factors are required for listening comprehension to be successful. The listener's dependence (in particular, characteristics such as the development of listening skills, memory, attention), listening conditions (speech speed, volume and form of language material) and the linguistic aspects of the used material are taken into account.

Guiding students in the process of listening not only gives them the knowledge to successfully perform the listening task, but also motivates them and takes control of their own knowledge. Thus, listening is an invisible mental process. Listening is an active skill, so more attention should be paid to the listening process in language teaching. Listeners need to distinguish

sounds, understand and interpret vocabulary and grammatical structures. Learning and teaching listening comprehension in a foreign language using modern and interactive technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, he can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons using computers. In addition, listening and watching foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs is one of the effective methods. The use of these technical tools makes the process of students' listening comprehension of a foreign language more interesting and effective.

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